

MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL FOR ON-BOARD-OPTIMIZED ATTITUDE GUIDANCE FOR COMETARY FLY-BY - PROBLEM STATEMENT, SOLUTIONS AND V&V PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Embedded on-board-optimization-based guidance is a set of guidance schemes that provide spacecraft the capability to plan and perform trajectories under several constraints autonomously. This autonomy will allow the space vehicle to more efficiently perform more challenging goals while dealing with rapidly changing environments, unmodelled/unforeseen dynamics and failure scenarios. However, the unique challenges of on-board applications raise the need for a thorough analysis of the computational efficiency, reliability, accuracy, and robustness of the solution process. This is directly related to how the guidance function is formulated, modelled, and analyzed, a process that should be founded on the understanding of the underlying physics and tailoring of the design to the specific problem. Verification and validation of such guidance schemes, wherever theoretically possible or empirical/numerically otherwise, is an important metric when evaluating the feasibility of the proposed solutions. This paper proposes a Model Predictive Control (MPC) approach to the constrained attitude guidance problem, applied to a cometary fly-by scenario. The problem is modeled as a convex quadratically constrained quadratic program (QCQP) form, to be solved numerically by means of a QCQP solver.

1 INTRODUCTION

In designing and implementing an optimization-based attitude guidance scheme, the goal can be to minimize the pointing error towards a target, the duration of a maneuver, minimize power and/or fuel or a combination of the previous. In terms of constraints, the spacecraft is bound by its dynamical behavior represented by the equation of motion and hardware limitations (such as actuator capabilities and exclusion/inclusion zones for safety of the payload). A direct representation of these goals and limitations into a standard mathematical representation of an optimization problem will lead, in general, to highly nonlinear nonconvex objective functions and constraints. Such optimization problems will easily fall under the category of NP-hard problems (non-deterministic polynomial-time hard). The main advantage of adopting an MPC [1] framework in the context of constrained attitude guidance problems, see e.g [2], is the ability to incorporate constraints in a systematic way. Constraints on inputs may, for instance, be exploited to model saturation of the actuators. Specifically, in this case, constraints might be imposed to limit the maximum torque allocated per reaction wheel, or the maximum torque that can be generated about each of the main axes (e.g. in case reaction control

thrusters are employed). Furthermore, in case of failure of an actuator, input constraints can be appropriately adapted, to modify the control strategy accordingly. Constraints involving state variables, instead, may be suitably employed to model exclusion/inclusion zones for sensitive instruments. The constrained attitude guidance problem will be first formulated in its most general form, which entails the nonlinearities due to the dynamics of the system. The structure of the problem is analyzed, and an approach to model it in a convex form is devised. Leveraging on such model, the optimization problem to be solved online is recast to a quadratically constrained quadratic program (QCQP). Starting from a non-linear non-convex optimization problem it is possible to obtain a convex optimization problem that can be classified as a QCQP through linearization of system dynamics and thoughtful and physically-grounded analysis of the underlying constraints. While the analysis of constraints can allow their translation into new costs or even transformation into adequate quadratic or linear constraints, the linearization of the dynamics is a required step since none of the typical attitude representations is linear. A time-varying trajectory is designed for the whole prediction horizon and then updated the next time the optimization is performed. Regardless, it is necessary to devise a strategy to compute the 4-D trajectories for the linearization. Taking advantage of the re-optimization with new navigation data and the optimal actuation, it is possible to update the previously generated trajectory set-points for the predicted horizon, thus iteratively approximating the actual optimal trajectory. This solves the problem of having a set-point trajectory that is too far from the optimal and that precludes the optimizer of finding the actual global optimum. However, it is still necessary to design an initial guess for the trajectory. That problem is tackled by designing a simple slew by inverting the dynamics analytically.

The increase of computational efficiency in the last decades has made it possible for scientists and engineers to turn their attention to the field of optimization. Especially, in subjects as complex as aerospace engineering, where robustness, accuracy and efficiency are of the utmost importance, optimization techniques are steadily becoming the standard rather than the deviation. Optimization solutions can range from trivial analytical derivations to very power and time consuming numerical methods. In fact, solving a generic nonlinear program (NLP), i.e. an optimization problem in which the objective function and the constraints are nonlinear, and not known to be convex, is challenging, even numerically. Indeed, finding the global optimum of a NLP might require a large amount of computations, even using methods like [3], which are often only valid for a small number of decision variables. Thus, such methods are unsuitable to be employed in embedded optimization, where computation time is a very strict requirement. On the other hand, for applications in which feasibility is of higher concern than global optimality (which is often the case in optimal control), methods to compute a point that *locally* minimizes the objective function can be employed (see e.g. [4]). In spite of the fact that the computed solution highly depends on the initial guess, such methods – among which we mention sequential quadratic programming (SQP) [5] and interior-point methods [6] – are effective and well-developed, and in some cases efficient and reliable enough to be employed in embedded applications, see e.g. [7], [8], [9].

Instead, in case the optimization problem to be addressed is known to be convex, which means the objective function and the feasible set are convex, convex optimization methods [10] can be employed in the numerical solution of the problem. Convexity of the problem guarantees existence and uniqueness of the solution. This means that any locally optimal point is also globally optimal. Also, the optimum can therefore be computed rather easily.

In the context of attitude guidance, we aim at controlling the rotational dynamics of the spacecraft. Such dynamics are described by Euler's equations, that are inherently nonlinear in the angular velocity of the spacecraft. Besides the angular velocity, the state space should also include a representation of the attitude of the spacecraft. In this respect, it should be mentioned that several representations

may be employed to describe the rotational degrees of freedom of a body in a 3D space, see e.g. [11]. Minimal parameterizations involving only 3 independent coordinates, such as Euler angles, inevitably suffer from the possible presence of representation singularities, and shall only be used in applications where these are not present. In space applications, unit quaternions or direction cosine matrix (DCM) parameterizations, are often preferred to describe the rotational kinematics of the spacecraft. This work is built around a unit quaternion parameterization of the orientation of a rigid body with respect to an inertial reference frame.

Real-time optimization-based algorithms for spacecraft reorientation have been successfully implemented in the past. We mention the works of [12, Section 14.2.2.3], which is more thoroughly clarified in [13], and [14] as some of the most recent applications of a technique entitled *successive convexification* to achieve constrained optimal vehicle reorientation.

Our work diverges from those mentioned before, since our goal is to study the applicability of a model predictive control framework to the problem of optimal on-board attitude guidance. Also, this research is not based on a successive convexification algorithm, but instead in the *one-shot solution* to a convexified optimization problem. This procedure is employed for all iterations of the MPC algorithm.

This paper presents a preliminary study in the beginning of a journey towards the implementation of MPC-based on-board optimization algorithms for the control of spacecraft orientation in scenarios where autonomous adaptation to changing conditions is of the utmost importance. After fully describing the mathematics of the problem, we shall focus on the major issues that are inherent to the problem at hand. Of these, we mention the translation of highly nonlinear dynamical constraints into convex ones, always having in mind how coarse discretization methods and poorly chosen sampling times, might affect the performance and overall run-time of the proposed solution. Our work will have a special emphasis on making use of problem specific properties in order to simplify and ultimately accelerate, for instance, the discretization methods employed. Adding to the problem of CPU run-time, we acknowledge that current processing capabilities of orbital vehicles are still a challenge; this, in turn, calls for a serious study of the impact of MPC parameters such as prediction and control horizons as well as sample time on achievable performance, and the fading line between guidance and control. By the end of this study, it is our goal to have determined the performance and the real-world applicability of this approach, where only one call to a convex solver is performed in each iteration of the MPC algorithm, and the reference trajectory is updated between iterations. We venture the guess that a *successive convexification*-like approach embedded in an efficiently designed model predictive control framework should be the best approach in terms of achievable performance. Nevertheless, it is our goal to determine whether other methods, like the one we envision, might provide comparable performance with a significantly lower computational burden to on-board computers. Having this in mind, we intend to produce a comprehensive comparison between our approach and other alternatives. Here, we shall focus on the possible combinations of the two key aspects of the algorithms. These are:

- Whether they allow, or not, for the update of the reference trajectory, even if only within a trust region.
- Whether it is worth it to iteratively refine the solution to the optimization problem in each MPC step, or the refinement of the set trajectory from one MPC step to the next is enough, allowing to consider the one-shot convexification.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

This paper addresses the attitude guidance and control (G&C) of a spacecraft performing a cometary fly-by. More precisely, the studied scenario regards the crucial phase of the fly-by, when the spacecraft comes nearest to the comet. In this phase, assuming the comet needs to be in line of sight (LOS) of an instrument, e.g. a visual or infrared camera, some type of actuation needs to be performed in order to attain such requirement. A simple approach would be to change the orientation of the instrument and point it towards the comet. This approach, however, might fail due to the spacecraft blocking any possible LOS to the comet. To overcome this issue, the entire spacecraft would have to be subject to an attitude re-orientation to allow for the mission to be successfully accomplished. This work is based on the assumption that the comet stays in the LOS of the instrument during the fly-by by means of a rotation, or slew, of the entire spacecraft.

Let us parameterize the attitude of the vehicle in terms of the quaternion

$$\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} q_w \\ \mathbf{q}_v \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} q_w \\ q_x \\ q_y \\ q_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\{q_w, q_x, q_y, q_z\} \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{q} = 1$. The quaternion \mathbf{q} transforms a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ expressed in $\{B\}$, the body-fixed coordinate frame, into a vector ${}^I \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ expressed in $\{I\}$, the local coordinate inertial reference frame.

The rotational kinematics can be written as

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}(t) \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the angular velocity of the vehicle expressed in $\{B\}$, and \otimes represents the quaternion product as described in [15].

Assuming the attitude of the spacecraft can only be controlled through a set of n_w reaction wheels (RW), the dynamics of the system is defined as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{J} \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t) = (\mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) + \mathbf{L} \mathbf{h}(t)) \times \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) - \mathbf{L} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{T}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{h}}(t) = \mathbf{u}(t) \end{cases}. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix of the vehicle expressed in $\{B\}$ (assumed constant, neglecting possible mass distribution changes), $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$ is the angular momentum stored in each reaction wheel, $\mathbf{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n_w}$ is the reaction wheel torque distribution matrix, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$ is the motor torque to be applied to each of the reaction wheels, and $\mathbf{T}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ other torques that might affect the spacecraft's dynamics, e.g. fuel sloshing, solar array flexible modes, gravity gradient.

The cosine of the angle, θ_{BC} , between the unitary vector $\mathbf{d}_B \in \mathbb{R}^3$, representative of the instrument's boresight direction expressed in $\{B\}$, and the unitary vector $\mathbf{d}_C \in \mathbb{R}^3$ representative of the direction to the comet expressed in body-fixed coordinates, can be written as

$$\cos(\theta_{BC}) = \mathbf{d}_B^T \mathbf{d}_C. \quad (4)$$

In the case that only the relative position, in inertial coordinates ${}^I \mathbf{r}$, between the comet and the spacecraft is known, the vector \mathbf{d}_C can be computed resorting to

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{d}_C \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{q}^* \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ {}^I \mathbf{d}_C \end{bmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{q}, \quad (5)$$

where ${}^I\mathbf{d}_C$ is the unitary vector $\frac{{}^I\mathbf{r}}{\|{}^I\mathbf{r}\|}$.

The main objective of this work is to make use of well studied optimization concepts to obtain a G&C algorithm that allows the spacecraft to keep the comet as best as possible in the LOS of the instruments, i.e. to minimize the angle θ_{BC} throughout the fly-by.

3 OPTIMIZATION

Let us define the nonlinear state space system representative of the kinematics and dynamics of the spacecraft's attitude, presented in (2) and (3),

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = f(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\mathbf{q}^T(t), \boldsymbol{\omega}^T(t), \mathbf{h}^T(t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{(4+3+n_w)}$ and $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$

In a broad sense, an optimal control problem can be defined as finding, possibly subject to some constraints, the input to a system that minimizes a cost function. In the problem at hands, we want to find the input, \mathbf{u} , that minimizes, between two arbitrary time instants, a cost function J , subject to the nonlinear dynamics of the system and to constraints on the input and on the state. Formally, we have the nonlinear and, possibly, nonconvex optimal control problem

$$\begin{aligned} \underset{\mathbf{u}}{\text{minimize}} \quad & J = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} L(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) dt \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = f(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \\ & c(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

These types of problems pose a lot of challenges, namely because of the potentially nonconvex cost function J , the nonlinear dynamics and the possibly nonconvex inequality constraints. Furthermore, we are dealing with an infinite dimensional problem, since the cost function is defined for all time instants t from t_0 to t_f . To work around these issues we start by addressing the problems of nonconvexity and nonlinearity.

3.1 Convexification

Combining (4) and (5), yields the following quadratic form

$$\cos(\theta_{BC}) = 1 - \mathbf{q}^T \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{d}_B^T \\ \mathbf{d}_B & -[\mathbf{d}_B]_{\times} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -{}^I\mathbf{d}_C^T \\ {}^I\mathbf{d}_C & [{}^I\mathbf{d}_C]_{\times} \end{bmatrix} + I \right) \mathbf{q} = 1 - \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{q}, \quad (8)$$

where $[\mathbf{a}]_{\times}$ is the 3-by-3 skew-symmetric commonly associated with the cross product, and \mathbf{M} is, by definition, a positive semi-definite matrix, since $-1 < \cos(\theta_{BC}) < 1$. During the fly-by maneuver we want to be able to minimize the angle θ_{BC} , indicative of the pointing error to the comet. Also, we want to minimize the power needed to obtain such objective. Having this in mind, we can write the following cost function

$$J = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} (\mathbf{x}^T(t) \mathbf{Q}_J(t) \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{u}^T(t) \mathbf{R}_J(t) \mathbf{u}(t)) dt, \quad (9)$$

which combines the cost of not pointing to the comet and the total power needed to perform the mission. Note that \mathbf{Q}_J is the diagonal matrix $\text{diag}(\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0})$, which is positive semidefinite. The positive semidefiniteness of the matrix \mathbf{R}_J can also be ensured. The problem of having a possibly nonconvex cost function is now solved.

3.2 Linearization

Regarding the nonlinear dynamics, these can be linearized around a nominal trajectory. Assuming that the states $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$ and $\mathbf{h}(t)$ can be represented by the sum of a nominal component plus a deviation (or error) from the nominal value, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) = \bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t) + \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$ and $\mathbf{h}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{h}}(t) + \delta\mathbf{h}(t)$, the linearization of the equations presented in (3) is, after some manipulation and discarding terms of second and higher orders,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{J}\delta\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t) = ([\mathbf{J}\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t)]_{\times} - [\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t)]_{\times}\mathbf{J} + [\mathbf{L}\bar{\mathbf{h}}(t)]_{\times})\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) - \mathbf{J}^{-1}[\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t)]_{\times}\mathbf{L}\delta\mathbf{h}(t) - \mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{L}\delta\mathbf{u}(t) \\ \delta\dot{\mathbf{h}}(t) = \delta\mathbf{u}(t) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

In what concerns the quaternion kinematics (2), the linearization procedure requires a more in-depth analysis, since the quaternion \mathbf{q} cannot be written as a sum of a nominal component $\bar{\mathbf{q}}(t)$ plus a deviation $\delta\mathbf{q}(t)$, as the result would not be a unit quaternion. Rather, the quaternion product $\mathbf{q}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{q}}(t) \otimes \delta\mathbf{q}(t)$ is true. The solution presented in [15, p. 57] yields the linear relation (note $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is not the same as the angle θ_{BC} enunciated in (4) and (8))

$$\delta\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) = -[\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t)]_{\times}\delta\boldsymbol{\theta}(t) + \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t), \quad (11)$$

where $[0 \ \delta\boldsymbol{\theta}^T]^T = 2\delta\mathbf{q}$.

Combining (10) and (11) yields the linear time-varying system

$$\delta\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}, t)\delta\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\delta\mathbf{u}(t). \quad (12)$$

Here, $\delta\mathbf{x} = [\delta\boldsymbol{\theta}^T, \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}^T, \delta\mathbf{h}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{(3+3+n_w)}$, and the matrices

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{B}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \\ \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3+3+n_w) \times (n_w)}$$

and

$$\mathbf{A}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}) = \left[\begin{array}{c|c|c} \mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} & \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \\ \hline \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}} & \mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}\mathbf{h}} \\ \hline \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{array} \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{(3+3+n_w) \times (3+3+n_w)}$$

are composed of $\mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = -[\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}]_{\times}$, $\mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \mathbf{J}^{-1}\{[\mathbf{J}\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}]_{\times} - [\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}}]_{\times}\mathbf{J} + [\mathbf{L}\bar{\mathbf{h}}]_{\times}\}$, $\mathbf{A}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}\mathbf{h}} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{L}$, and $\mathbf{B}_{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{L}$. Note that the time dependence is dropped for readability purposes.

The nominal values of the states and inputs can be obtained via the TRIAD method [16], and the inversion of the system dynamics. The TRIAD method allows us to obtain, in nominal conditions, the rotation matrices, and consequently the quaternions, representative of the attitude of the spacecraft during the fly-by. One of the vectors needed to make use of the TRIAD method is, obviously, the direction from the spacecraft to the comet. The second vector, that fixes the attitude of the spacecraft, was chosen as the direction perpendicular to the plane of the trajectory. In body coordinates, we want to match these directions to those of the instrument's boresight and the solar panels' orientation, respectively. The choice of keeping the solar panels in a direction perpendicular to the fly-by trajectory allows them to be, in this specific case, illuminated by the sun during the maneuver.

Being the nominal attitude determined, the angular velocity of the spacecraft, $\boldsymbol{\omega}$, can be computed by solving the differential equation (2). Finally, the nominal values of the angular momentum \mathbf{h} in each of the reaction wheels, as well as those of the inputs \mathbf{u} , can be iteratively determined through (3).

3.3 Discretization

At this point, the optimal control problem is now guaranteed to be convex and subject to linear equality constraints imposed by the system's dynamics. Nevertheless, the problem of infinite dimensionality still persists. To tackle this, a discretization of the problem can be performed. The continuous-time cost function is easily discretized by transforming the integral into a sum over all discrete-time instants as

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{k=k(t_f)} \left(\mathbf{x}^T(t_k) \mathbf{Q}_J(t_k) \mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{u}^T(t_k) \mathbf{R}_J(t_k) \mathbf{u}(t_k) \right). \quad (13)$$

As for the dynamics-related equality constraints, these must be handled with more attention. Control Theory states that the continuous time-varying dynamical system (12) can be discretized as

$$\delta \mathbf{x}(t_{k+1}) = \Phi_{k+1|k}(\bar{\omega}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}) \delta \mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{G}_{k+1|k}(\bar{\omega}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}) \delta \mathbf{u}(t_k), \quad (14)$$

where the state transition matrix (STM) $\Phi_{k+1|k}$, and the input propagation matrix (IPM), $\mathbf{G}_{k+1|k}$, concentrate the solution to the dynamical system, i.e. they allow for the determination of the state $\delta \mathbf{x}$ at an arbitrary time step $k + 1$ as a linear combination of the state and the input in the previous time step k .

Several techniques can be employed to solve the ordinary differential equation (ODE) (12) and, consequently, obtain the STM and the IPM, being the most simple and expedite, the forward Euler method [17]. This method is based on the truncation of second and higher order terms of the Taylor series expansion of $\delta \mathbf{x}(t)$, and, as such, introduces, at every time-step, errors in the discretization process. This solution to an ODE assumes, for an arbitrary time step $h := t_{k+1} - t_k$, that

$$\dot{\delta \mathbf{x}} \approx \frac{\delta \mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \delta \mathbf{x}_k}{h}. \quad (15)$$

According to this approximation, the STM and IPM become, respectively,

$$\Phi_{k+1|k}(\bar{\omega}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}, k) = (\mathbf{I} + h \mathbf{A}(\bar{\omega}, \bar{\mathbf{h}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}}, k)) \quad (16)$$

and

$$\mathbf{G}_{k+1|k} = h \mathbf{B}. \quad (17)$$

Note that the system is time-varying, hence, for this method to work properly, we assume that between time-steps the time-varying dynamics matrix $\mathbf{A}(t)$ remains constant. Also, as previously stated, this method induces some errors on the discretization process, therefore, prior to implementation, it must be scrutinized to determine its applicability to the problem at hands. Even though preliminary analysis revealed promising results, the discretization process can also be performed through the following, more rigorous, method.

Recall the system of differential equations (12),

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\delta \boldsymbol{\theta}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_\theta \delta \boldsymbol{\theta}(t) + \delta \boldsymbol{\omega}(t), \\ \dot{\delta \boldsymbol{\omega}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_\omega \delta \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) + \mathbf{A}_{\omega \mathbf{h}} \delta \mathbf{h}(t) + \mathbf{B}_\omega \delta \mathbf{u}(t) \\ \dot{\delta \mathbf{h}}(t) = \delta \mathbf{u}(t) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Under the assumption that, in between time-steps, the input is constant. i.e. $\delta \mathbf{u}(t) = \delta \mathbf{u}$ for $t_k \leq t < t_{k+1}$, the solution of the last differential equation in (18) is

$$\delta\mathbf{h}(t) = \delta\mathbf{h}(t_k) + (t - t_k)\delta\mathbf{u}(t_k). \quad (19)$$

With respect to the solution of $\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$, the variation of constants method [18] provides the closed form

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, t_k)\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t_k) + \int_{t_k}^t \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, \tau)\mathbf{A}_{\omega\mathbf{h}}\delta\mathbf{h}(\tau)d\tau + \int_{t_k}^t \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, \tau)\mathbf{B}_\omega\delta\mathbf{u}(\tau)d\tau, \quad (20)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{\omega, k+1|k} := \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, t_k) = e^{(\mathbf{A}_\omega(t-t_k))}$. It should be noted that $\mathbf{A}_{\omega\mathbf{h}}$ is computed at time instant t_k .

Since $\delta\mathbf{h}(\tau)$ is known from (19), and $\delta\mathbf{u}(\tau)$ is assumed constant, the solution becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) &= \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, t_k)\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t_k) + \int_{t_k}^t \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, \tau)d\tau\mathbf{A}_{\omega\mathbf{h}}\delta\mathbf{h}(t_k) \\ &+ \int_{t_k}^t (\tau - t_k)\boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, \tau)d\tau\mathbf{A}_{\omega\mathbf{h}}\delta\mathbf{h}(t_k) + \int_{t_k}^t \boldsymbol{\Phi}_\omega(t, \tau)d\tau\mathbf{B}_\omega\delta\mathbf{u}(t_k), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where the integrals depend on the eigenvalues of the argument of the exponential. This expression can be more compactly written as

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) = e^{(\mathbf{A}_\omega(t-t_k))}\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t_k) + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{\omega\mathbf{h}}\delta\mathbf{h}(t_k) + \mathbf{G}_\omega\delta\mathbf{u}(t_k). \quad (22)$$

Knowing the solution to $\delta\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$, the same process can be applied to derive the solution to $\delta\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)$, here omitted due to space limitations. Ultimately, the solution of the linear system (12), valid for $t_k < t < t_{k+1}$, can be written as in (14), with the matrices

$$\boldsymbol{\Phi}(t, t_k) = \begin{bmatrix} e^{(\mathbf{A}_\theta(t-t_k))} & \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{\theta\omega} & \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{\theta\mathbf{h}} \\ \mathbf{0} & e^{(\mathbf{A}_\omega(t-t_k))} & \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{\omega\mathbf{h}} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

and

$$\mathbf{G}(t, t_k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_\theta \\ \mathbf{G}_\omega \\ (t - t_k)\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

The proposed solution can then be used to discretize the linear system (12) between arbitrary time instants t_k and t_{k+1} .

3.4 Constraints

The optimization process described so far has only introduced equality constraints related to the natural physics of the problem that must be verified during the maneuver. Nevertheless, as briefly discussed in section 3.2, there are other constraints that must be verified, such as keeping the solar arrays oriented perpendicular to the plane of the trajectory. Also, besides minimizing the pointing error of the instruments in relation to the comet we want to ensure that the latter stays in the field of view (FOV) of the instrument, i.e. there must be an inclusion zone where the attitude of the vehicle must lie within. Both these constraints can be mathematically formulated as inequalities as follows.

Recall from (8) that the cosine of the angle between the directions from the vehicle to the comet and that of the boresight of the instrument can be written as a quadratic function of the attitude-representative quaternion. As such, to maintain the comet within the FOV of the instrument this cosine

must be greater than or equal to the cosine of the FOV angle, θ_{FOV} , of the instrument. Formally, we want to verify, at all time instants, the inequality,

$$\mathbf{q}^T \underbrace{\left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{d}_B^T \\ \mathbf{d}_B & -[\mathbf{d}_B]_\times \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -{}^I\mathbf{d}_C^T \\ {}^I\mathbf{d}_C & [{}^I\mathbf{d}_C]_\times \end{bmatrix} + I \right)}_{\mathbf{M}_{\text{pointing}}} \mathbf{q} \leq 1 - \cos(\theta_{FOV}). \quad (25)$$

This represents a convex quadratic constraint, since the matrix in parenthesis is the same as that denoted by \mathbf{M} in (8), which is guaranteed to be positive semidefinite. It is important to note that, with this type of constraint the problem becomes a convex QCQP, which is, in general, more difficult to solve than a standard convex QP. In what concerns the solar panels' orientation, this can also be imposed as an inequality constraint similar to (25) by computing the inner product of \mathbf{d}_P , the direction of the main axis of the solar panels, in body coordinates, and \mathbf{d}_\perp , the direction, also in body coordinates, of the perpendicular to the trajectory plane. If only the inertial relative position ${}^I\mathbf{r}$ of the spacecraft, as well as its inertial relative velocity ${}^I\mathbf{v}$, are known, the direction ${}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp$ can be obtained via the cross product ${}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp = \frac{{}^I\mathbf{r}}{\|{}^I\mathbf{r}\|} \times \frac{{}^I\mathbf{v}}{\|{}^I\mathbf{v}\|}$. In body coordinates, this direction can be obtained via

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{d}_\perp \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{q}^* \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ {}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp \end{bmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{q}. \quad (26)$$

The aforementioned inner product yields

$$\mathbf{d}_P^T \mathbf{d}_\perp = 1 - \mathbf{q}^T \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{d}_P^T \\ \mathbf{d}_P & -[\mathbf{d}_P]_\times \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -{}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp^T \\ {}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp & [{}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp]_\times \end{bmatrix} + I \right) \mathbf{q} \quad (27)$$

which is the cosine between the desired orientation of the solar panels and their actual orientation. The relaxation of this constraint, i.e. by letting the panels be misaligned by a given angle, leads, in parallel to what happens with the pointing inclusion zones, to the quadratic inequality

$$\mathbf{q}^T \underbrace{\left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{d}_P^T \\ \mathbf{d}_P & -[\mathbf{d}_P]_\times \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -{}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp^T \\ {}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp & [{}^I\mathbf{d}_\perp]_\times \end{bmatrix} + I \right)}_{\mathbf{M}_{\text{panel}}} \mathbf{q} \leq 1 + \epsilon \quad (28)$$

Besides these constraints, and as is recurrent in control problems, both the states and the inputs might be subject to strict constraints. In this specific case, the control input \mathbf{u} and the angular momentum stored on the RWs \mathbf{h} are subject to so-called *box* constraints, in the sense that they are, component-wise, limited with an upper and lower limits. Using the operand \leq to denote component-wise inequalities, these previously put forward constraints can be formalized as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{\min} &\leq \mathbf{u}(t_k) \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max} \\ \mathbf{h}_{\min} &\leq \mathbf{h}(t_k) \leq \mathbf{h}_{\max} \end{aligned}, \quad (29)$$

which are convex.

The final constraint needed to fully characterize the dynamics of the system is one that imposes an initial condition on the states. This is, in practice, a value of each of the states, provided by the navigation system on board of the spacecraft, at the beginning of the optimization process. Formally, $\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0$.

3.5 Relaxation

As stated in Section 3.4 with regard to the orientation of the solar panels, a constraint might be relaxed using slack parameters, such as ϵ on (28).

Constraint relaxation must be treated with special attention since it alters the properties of the optimization problem. For instance, although mathematically we could relax the box constraints (29) without any problem, it would allow for the solution of the optimization problem to lie in a region where the states and/or inputs cannot be physically possible to apply or attain. This procedure can be used, in the problem at hands, to allow for the cosine of the pointing error to be even bigger than the cosine of the FOV of the instrument during some parts of the maneuver, which might reduce the overall consumption of power required by the actuators, and thus be of interest to other mission requirements. With this in mind, the slack variable used to allow for the relaxation of the constraints must be incorporated in the cost function as to minimize their impact on the solution of the problem. Using the same slack variable ϵ as in (28), the inequality constraint (25) becomes

$$\mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{M}_{\text{pointing}} \mathbf{q} \leq 1 - \cos(\theta_{FOV}) + \epsilon, \quad (30)$$

and the cost function is set to minimize the square of the slack variable, making (13) become

$$J = \rho \epsilon^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{k=k(t_f)} (\mathbf{x}^T(t_k) \mathbf{Q}_J(t_k) \mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{u}^T(t_k) \mathbf{R}_J(t_k) \mathbf{u}(t_k)). \quad (31)$$

Here, the parameter ρ is making it possible for the impact of the slack variable in the optimization problem to be modulated by the designer. Finally, since we want this slack variable to represent an addition to the maximum deviation to the desired attitude, the convex constraint $\epsilon > 0$ is appended to the set of constraints already described.

4 MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

The optimization problem described so far has been defined as minimizing a cost index computed at discrete time steps starting and finishing at arbitrary instants, t_0 and t_f , respectively. The next logical step should be to define these time instants so as to maximize the benefits of the optimization process as a whole.

A simple approach would be to perform the optimization process for the entire duration of the maneuver. This guidance algorithm would output, at the beginning of the maneuver, the sequence of control inputs necessary to achieve the requirements imposed by the constraints. The main disadvantage of this line of action is that, in the advent of a change of environmental conditions and/or actuator failures, the system would be incapable of correcting by itself the guidance previously computed, then overloading any other control system working in parallel to the optimization-based G&C scheme here described.

To tackle this problem, the optimization process can be set to be solved at every arbitrary time-step after the beginning of the maneuver. Also, the so-called prediction horizon, during which the cost function is computed as well as the constraints are set to be verified, can be of different length than that of the entire maneuver. Simply put, this is what the ever-spreading technique of model predictive control proposes: the computation, at each time-step, of the solution to an optimization problem, which incorporates a prediction of the future behavior of a well modeled dynamic system subject to constraints. The repetition of this process during the entire maneuver, makes for the apparent *receding* of the prediction horizon, reason why the MPC is commonly referred to as a *receding horizon* algorithm. Fig. 1 illustrates this.

Figure 1: Receding horizon in the MPC framework.

Besides actuating the reaction wheels with the first entry of the sequence of optimal control inputs, as is common in the MPC framework, we also utilize the outputted optimal sequence of states to update the nominal trajectory around which the linearizations are performed. This allows for a solid integration of the MPC theory in our specific problem.

Model predictive control has the benefit of being more robust to changes of the surrounding environment and being able to react to possible intra/extravehicular disturbances. Its major drawback, and by far, the biggest impediment to its use in critical applications such as spacecraft guidance is that, in between time steps, a considerable-size optimization problem has to be guaranteed to be solved, under penalty of the whole system failing due to a non responsive guidance algorithm. This is a very important aspect to be considered and analyzed during the development of this type of optimal guidance solutions. Besides selecting/developing a fast and accurate solver capable of handling, in a timely manner, the optimization problem, a study of the impact, on the size and/or solvability in real time of the optimization problem, of changing the prediction horizon and/or the length of the discrete time-steps must be carried out.

For a generic prediction horizon of N time steps, the mathematical formulation of the optimization problem to be solved at every sampling time is

$$\begin{aligned}
\underset{\mathbf{V}}{\text{minimize}} \quad & J = \rho\epsilon^2 + \sum_{k=0}^N (\delta\mathbf{x}^T(t_k)\mathbf{Q}(t_k)\delta\mathbf{x}(t_k) + \delta\mathbf{u}^T(t_k)\mathbf{R}_J(t_k)\delta\mathbf{u}(t_k)) . \\
\text{subject to} \quad & \delta\mathbf{x}(t_{k+1}) = \mathbf{\Phi}(t_{k+1}, t_k)\delta\mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{G}(t_{k+1}, t_k)\delta\mathbf{u}(t_k), \\
& \mathbf{q}^T(t_k)\mathbf{M}_{\text{pointing}}\mathbf{q}(t_k) \leq 1 - \cos(\theta_{FOV}) + \epsilon \\
& \mathbf{q}^T(t_k)\mathbf{M}_{\text{panel}}\mathbf{q}(t_k) \leq 1 + \epsilon \\
& \delta\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \delta\mathbf{x}_0 \\
& \mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}(t_k) \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max} \\
& \mathbf{h}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{h}(t_k) \leq \mathbf{h}_{\max} \\
& \epsilon > 0
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Being the optimization variables $\mathbf{V} = [\delta\mathbf{X}^T \ \delta\mathbf{U}^T \ \epsilon]^T$, where $\mathbf{X} = [\delta\mathbf{x}^T(t_0) \ \dots \ \delta\mathbf{x}^T(t_N)]^T$ and $\mathbf{U} = [\delta\mathbf{u}^T(t_0) \ \dots \ \delta\mathbf{u}^T(t_N)]^T$. Here $\delta\mathbf{x} = [\delta\boldsymbol{\theta}^T \ \delta\mathbf{w}^T \ \delta\mathbf{h}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{3+3+n_w}$. Note that \mathbf{q} can be written as $\bar{\mathbf{q}} \otimes \delta\mathbf{q}$, being $\delta\boldsymbol{\theta}$ obtained from $[0 \ \delta\boldsymbol{\theta}^T]^T = 2\delta\mathbf{q}$. Moreover, the states $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and \mathbf{h} , and the input \mathbf{u} can be written, respectively, as $\bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}} + \delta\boldsymbol{\omega}$, $\bar{\mathbf{h}} + \delta\mathbf{h}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\mathbf{u}$. It is also worth mentioning that the matrix \mathbf{Q} in (32) is not the same as in (9), but rather one that includes the transformations from \mathbf{x} to $\delta\mathbf{x}$ previously presented.

Figure 2 presents a block diagram visualization of the G&C method proposed in this work.

Figure 2: Convex Optimization-based G&C block diagram.

The *Composition* and *Decomposition* blocks allow for the change between each of the variables and its decomposition into a function of their nominal condition and a deviation from the nominal condition. A special remark has to be made regarding the composition of the quaternions from $\delta\theta$. Since the optimization process has no constraint specifically tailored to maintain the unitary property of the attitude-representative quaternions, the deviation from the nominal quaternion is defined as $\delta\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\|\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\|) & \sin(\|\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\|) \frac{\delta\theta}{\|\delta\theta\|} \end{bmatrix}^T$, thus making the aforementioned property always true.

5 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Having the Comet Interceptor mission scenario [12] as a case for the study of optimization-based G&C, we firstly consider, for preliminary testing purposes, that the spacecraft is following an approximately rectilinear trajectory like the one represented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Fly-by approximately rectilinear trajectory.

The dashed blue lines indicate the direction from the spacecraft to the comet (in red), and the solid blue lines the desired instrument's boresight direction. The sought for orientation of the solar panels is also depicted in the green lines. This trajectory is performed at a constant relative speed of 70 km/s, being the closest approach to the comet at a distance of 1000 km, and the full duration of this symmetrical trajectory of 200 seconds. The spacecraft is equipped with 4 reaction wheels capable of controlling, in all axes, its orientation.

5.1 Nominal trajectories

As stated in section 3.2, for the optimization process to be conducted, a linearization of the rotational dynamics of the system has to be performed. This includes an execution of the TRIAD method, which provides the values of $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$. Having the values of the nominal orientation, the angular velocity of the

spacecraft can be determined through integration of (2). Finally, the values of the angular momentum and control inputs to be applied to each of the reaction wheels can be obtained iteratively via (3). The results of this set of procedures is depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Nominal trajectories (color) and limits (dashed).

As expected, due to the nature of the trajectory, all the states and inputs present a symmetry relative to the closest approach instant.

An iteration of the optimization-based guidance is provided in Fig. 5. This is a result of setting the prediction horizon for the entirety of the trajectory, i.e., for the whole 200 seconds, and starting with a perfect pointing to the comet. A heavy weight was associated to the slack variable ϵ as to minimize the need for its use in the solution of the problem, thus making the constraints as *hard* as possible. Also a *box* constraint on both the angular momentum and input torque was imposed. These limitations were set, as for mission specifications, at 3.2Nms and 0.17Nm for the angular momentum and input torque, respectively.

Figure 5: Optimization-based trajectory(color) and limits (dashed).

The optimization algorithm handles these constraints, as expected, and outputs a sequence of optimal control inputs.

A simulator of the real translational and rotational dynamics of the spacecraft was fed with the inputs from both the TRIAD method and the optimization-based guidance. Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the pointing errors during the maneuver.

Figure 6: Open-loop pointing errors.

As can be seen, while starting with a perfect pointing, both inputs lead to increasing pointing errors as the mission progresses. This is a clear effect of the saturation imposed in this specific scenario. The result of using the control sequence from the optimization process is, in this open-loop control scheme, worse than that which assumes the nominal values of the torque to be applied. Nevertheless, a fully functional closed-loop model predictive control scheme is expected to achieve considerably better results.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work has set the corner stone for our study of how on-board optimization methods can be employed in a model predictive control framework to overcome some of the issues inherent to most of the standard control algorithms, namely the robustness to changes in the surrounding environment, as well as in the on-board actuation systems.

The presented algorithm considers some of the most common constraints associated to the attitude guidance and control problem. The incorporation of attitude exclusion zones, a payload safety constraint, although resulting in an increasing complexity of the problem (due to their nonconvex nature), is one of the next steps on the road to achieving the real-world applicability of this guidance and control method.

One of the key aspects of the algorithm concerns the linearization of the highly nonlinear system that describes the rotational dynamics of the vehicle, since a trajectory, around which the system is linearized, must be obtained. For this end, we used a combination of the TRIAD method and an inversion of the dynamics, but future work could address this issue by making use of some of the ever-growing machine learning techniques, such as neural networks. Besides an initial linearization, the MPC framework requires the system to be linearized over consecutive receding prediction horizons; with respect to this matter, our approach was to update the previous trajectory with the solution to the optimal control problem, with no regards for how much the trajectory could deviate from the initial guess over time. Although it is intuitive to think that this is a promising approach, other methods, like keeping the trajectory as close as possible to the original one, should be studied.

The discretization of the continuous-time system representative of the system dynamics is also a concerning point of the algorithm. As discussed in the document, several classic approaches can be employed to this end. Nonetheless, an in-depth study of the impact on algorithm performance of which method and sampling frequency, combined with the MPC framework's prediction horizon length, must be carried out.

Another point worth mentioning are the algorithms and software used to solve the optimization problem. Although the theory of convex optimization provides the guarantee that a solution to the problem

is unique and optimal, this has to be computed in real time within a limited interval. To this end an adequate solver and optimization software must be selected or developed. It is our current objective to implement such tools in order to provide future support for other mission scenarios that might benefit from on-board optimization-based guidance and control.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Rawlings and D. Mayne, *Model Predictive Control: Theory and Design*, 2009.
- [2] A. Guiggiani, I. Kolmanovsky, P. Patrinos, and A. Bemporad, “Fixed-point constrained model predictive control of spacecraft attitude,” in *2015 American Control Conference (ACC)*, 2015, pp. 2317–2322.
- [3] L. Rios and N. Sahinidis, “Derivative-free optimization: A review of algorithms and comparison of software implementations,” *Journal of Global Optimization*, vol. 56, 2009.
- [4] J. Nocedal and S. J. Wright, *Numerical Optimization*, 2nd ed. Springer, 2006.
- [5] P. Boggs and J. Tolle, “Sequential quadratic programming,” *Acta Numerica*, vol. 4, pp. 1–51, 1995.
- [6] M. H. Wright, “Interior methods for constrained optimization,” *Acta Numerica*, vol. 1, p. 341–407, 1992.
- [7] A. Zanelli, A. Domahidi, J. Jerez, and M. Morari, “FORCES NLP: An efficient implementation of interior-point methods for multistage nonlinear nonconvex programs,” *International Journal of Control*, vol. 93, pp. 1–26, 2017.
- [8] P. Gill, W. Murray, and M. Saunders, “SNOPT: An SQP algorithm for large-scale constrained optimization,” *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 12, pp. 979–1006, 2002.
- [9] P. Sopasakis, E. Fresk, and P. Patrinos, “OpEn: Code generation for embedded nonconvex optimization,” *21th IFAC World Congress*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 6548–6554, 2020.
- [10] S. Boyd and L. Vandenberghe, *Convex Optimization*. Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- [11] M. Shuster, “A survey of attitude representation,” *Journal of The Astronautical Sciences*, vol. 41, pp. 439–517, 1993.
- [12] ESA, *CDF Study Report: Comet Interceptor- Assessment of Mission to Intercept a Long Period Comet or Interplanetary Object*, 2019.
- [13] V. Preda, A. Hyslop, and S. Bennani, “Optimal science-time reorientation policy for the comet interceptor flyby via sequential convex programming,” *CEAS Space Journal*, 2021.
- [14] T. Reynolds, C. Kelly, C. Morgan, A. Grebovic, J. Erickson, H. Brown, W. Pope, J. Casamayor, K. Kearsley, G. Caylak, K. Fisher, C. Wutzke, K. Ashton, J. Rosenthal, D. Tormey, E. Freneau, G. Giddings, H. Horata, A. Dighde, and A. Hunt, “Soc-i: A cubesat demonstration of optimization-based real-time constrained attitude control,” 2021.
- [15] J. Solà, “Quaternion kinematics for the error-state Kalman filter,” *arXiv:1711.02508 [cs]*, Nov. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1711.02508>
- [16] H. Black, “A passive system for determining the attitude of a satellite,” *AIAA Journal*, vol. 2, pp. 1350–1351, 1964.
- [17] D. S. Kendall Atkinson, Weimin Han, *Numerical Solution of Ordinary Differential Equations*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118164495.ch2>
- [18] E. A. Coddington and N. Levinson, *Theory of ordinary differential equations*. McGraw-Hill New York, 1955.